

Exploring the Intellectual and Social Dynamics of Food Sector Research in the Context of Climate Change: A Bibliometric Analysis

ABSTRACT

This paper explores the cross-fertilisation of literature between the food sector and climate change fields by performing a bibliometric analysis. 3,714 papers were retrieved from the Scopus database. Bibliographic coupling identified sixteen literature streams and their compositions. Co-authorship network analysis explored scholarly social communities. Comparing clustering results from both analyses assessed whether the intellectual closeness of communities was also social. Findings reveal that authors who mostly contributed to the two fields often participated cross-sectionally, touching upon various literature streams. Even when authors mainly dealt with one topic, they did so within heterogeneous research groups. Implications include directions for future research agenda.

***Keywords:** Bibliographic coupling analysis; Climate change; Co-authorship network; Food sector.*

Appendix

Supplementary Figure S1. The steps completed for the bibliometric analysis in this study. Adapted from Donthu *et al.* (2021), Öztürk *et al.* (2024) and Shi *et al.* (2024). Source: Authors.

Supplementary Figure S2. Distribution of documents per author, journal and country

Note: The vertical axes relative to the number of authors and journals and the horizontal axis relative to the number of documents per country are on a square root scale.

Supplementary Figure S3. Distribution of authors, journals and countries per number of received citations

Note: In the authors' and journals' graphs, both vertical and horizontal axes are on a square root scale. In the countries' graph, the horizontal axis is on a square root scale.

Supplementary Figure S4. Trends over time (1974-2022) for 16 clusters

Supplementary Figure S5. Trends over time (1986-2005) for 16 clusters

Supplementary Figure S6. Trends over time (2006-2022) for clusters 1-6

Supplementary Figure S7. Trends over time (2006-2022) for clusters 7-12

Supplementary Figure S8. Trends over time (2006-2022) for clusters 13-16

Supplementary Table S1.

Initial overview of the intersection of the food sector and climate change fields

Source	No. of documents returned (n=104)	No. of relevant documents (n=24)
Latest updated check for all sources: 13 March 2025		
Databases		
All fields and no timeframe; n=16 relevant documents		
Web of Science (WoS) database	43	11
Scopus database	37	5*
Five top journals in Agronomy and Crop Science, Food Science, Agricultural and Biological Sciences, and General Agricultural and Biological Sciences (adjusted for the study's relevance from CiteScore, 2023); Timeframe: 2015-2025; n=6 relevant documents		
Nature Sustainability	2	0
Trends in Food Science and Technology	10	3
Nature Food	0	0
Comprehensive Reviews in Food Science and Food Safety	6	3
Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition	2	0
Five top journals in Renewable Energy, Sustainability and the Environment, and Environmental Science (adjusted for the study's relevance from CiteScore, 2023); Timeframe: 2015-2025; n=2 relevant documents		
Nature Energy	0	0
Nature Reviews Earth and Environment	0	0
Energy and Environmental Science	0	0
Nature Climate Change	2	1
Applied Catalysis B: Environmental	2	1

Note: Five publications refer to relevant documents that featured in Scopus but not in WoS.

Supplementary Table S2.

Clusters' content description in terms of word frequency and codes run in NVivo

Cluster	10 most frequent words	1 st stage coding	2 nd stage coding
1	Foods, Products, Emissions, Using, Agriculture, 2009, Changing, Impacts, Consumption, Sustaining	Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and food choices	Diet shift
2	Waters, Using, Changing, Products, Agriculture, Foods, Climatic, Globally, Lands, Models	Land and water scarcity	Water management
3	Changing, Climatic, Agriculture, Foods, Crops, Adaptive, Farmers', Farms, Households', Products	Adaptation to climate change - farm level	Fields interviews
4	Plants, Doi, Crops, Changing, Using, Agricultural, Climatic, Foods, Products, Increase	Adapting crop or plant production to climate change	Agriculture and nutrient production for sustainability
5	Urbanizing, Foods, Agriculture', Farms, Products, Systems, City, Using, Sustained, Changing	Urban farming and innovation techniques	Food system adaptation for sustainability
6	Soils'', Crop', Increasingly, Agriculture, Using, Lands, Plants, Organs, Products, Yield'	Soil management for sustainable agro-ecosystems	Soil carbon sequestration
7	Changing, Using, Climatic, Products, Species', Foods, Model, Populations, Globally, Increase	Climate change impact on marine fisheries	Pest management
8	Changing, Climatic, Crops, Products, Foods, Model, Scenarios, Water, Agricultural, Yield	Adaptation of food systems to climate change and food security issues	Impact of climate change and CO ₂ on global agriculture
9	Crops, Soils, Emissions, Using, Products, Agriculture, Fertilizers, Energy, Waters, Increasingly	Nitrogen dynamics and climate change	Biofuel impact on water use changes
10	Yields, Crops, Climatic, Maize, Changing, Irrigation, Water, Model, Impacts, Agricultural	Climate change scenarios and water availability for food production	Climate change impact on crop yield
11	Foods, Agriculture, Using, Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), Systems, Crops, Products, Globally, Change, Data	Satellite Remote Sensing	Green technologies - sustainable intensification and low input production
12	Foods, Risks, Disease, Changing, Increased, Products, Maye, Infections, Climate, Safety	Impact of climate change, food safety and foodborne diseases on food security	Changing dietary habits
13	Food', Products, Agricultural, Lands, Globally, Using, Crops, Changing, Increase, Climatic	Climate change and land use adaptation for the global food system	Climate change and sustainable food production
14	Ozone, Changing, Crops, Plants, Climate, Effects, Concentrations, Global, Increasingly, Products	Ozone (O ₃), carbon dioxide (CO ₂) and N-cycle dynamics and impacts on agri-food systems	Projecting the impact of climate change under GHG emission scenarios
15	Plants, Foods, Research, Using, Stomatal, Crops', Collaborators, Development, Species, Doi	Techniques for sustainable food production and mitigate climate change	Incorporating underutilised crop species
16	Using, Data, Systems, Based, Network', Imaging, Computing, Security, Methods, Algorithms	Using technology for sustainability	Future beliefs and behaviours

Note: The codes presented in this table have been selected from those located in more files and that have received more references. For this analysis, "Reference" means the presence of the code in several parts of the same text or different texts.

Supplementary Table S3. Key topics in each cluster

Cluster	Key Topics	Highlights
1 Food Choices	Adopting diets with a reduced environmental impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Campaigns promoting dietary changes offer an efficient approach to reducing greenhouse gas emissions (Heller <i>et al.</i>, 2018). • The production of foods from animal sources accounts for the majority of agricultural emissions (Friel <i>et al.</i>, 2009).
2 Water Management	The expected rise in competition for global land and water resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is unclear how much agricultural technological progress can effectively adapt to changing trends (Lotze-Campen <i>et al.</i>, 2008). • This literature discussed the role of investment in increasing food crop productivity, improving irrigation system management, establishing novel systems, and rehabilitating depleted land and water resources.
3 Climate Adaptation	Sustainable practices implemented at a farm level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluating the efficacy of current efforts to adapt farms to climate change is critical for understanding their efficacy and recommending additional policy-level actions (Abid <i>et al.</i>, 2016). • It is crucial to research the adoption of novel farming technology and practices to understand better farmers' challenges (Steenwerth <i>et al.</i>, 2014).
4 Sustainable Crop Tech	Adapting crop/plant production to climate change and protecting plants' genetic diversity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The tendency is to make diversity easily accessible to plant breeders, allowing them to develop varieties that are well-suited to the new climatic conditions that farmers are already experiencing, particularly in developing regions (Dempewolf <i>et al.</i>, 2014). • Crop improvement becomes even more critical to ensuring long-term food production (Varshney <i>et al.</i>, 2011).
5 Food Systems and Urban Farming	Adaptation of plant, animal and food systems to changing environmental conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food system vulnerability extends beyond developing countries but is especially prevalent among impoverished populations; hence, the majority of production growth must occur in developing countries, which not only have lower average yield levels but also face significant environmental challenges (Fresco, 2009). • There is a need to implement publicly-driven multifunctional policies to encourage diversified production and programs that promote localised food systems to increase farmer autonomy (Rotz and Fraser, 2015).
6 Sustainable Soil Management	The use of intercropping to improve resource utilisation and agricultural productivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intercropping provides greater yield stability across climates than monocultures (Raseduzzaman and Jensen, 2017). • Exogenous application of humic substances in agricultural systems can help to advance environmentally responsible intensification practices (Canellas <i>et al.</i>, 2015)
7 Sustainable Agriculture and Aquaculture	Impact of climate change on agricultural practices and marine fisheries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preventing overfishing and developing management strategies that can effectively adapt to changes in productivity are critical to ensuring the long-term viability of marine ecosystems (Free <i>et al.</i>, 2019). • Enhancing the knowledge of dispersal mechanisms is vital for implementing sustainable pest management strategies (Mazzi and Dorn, 2012).

Supplementary Table S3. Key topics in each cluster - Continued

Cluster	Key Topics	Highlights
8 Climate-Agro Impacts	Factors influencing farm households' decisions to adapt to climate change	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to credit, extension services, and information were farm households' primary drivers of adaptation (Di Falco <i>et al.</i>, 2011).
9 Sustainable Bioenergy	Anthropogenic nitrogen and its role in climate change	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agriculture and industry have had a significant impact on the nitrogen cycle, with local and global environmental consequences (Shibata <i>et al.</i>, 2015). • There is an urgent need to improve nitrogen utilisation efficiency through effective field management practices; this is critical for protecting water resources and lowering greenhouse gas emissions (Snyder <i>et al.</i>, 2009).
10 Impacts on Water and Crops	Crop models critical in assessing the threat of climate change	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improving irrigation capacity and efficiency in rainfed systems should be combined with efforts to enhance water use efficiency and soil conservation, as these measures have been shown to increase crop yields while not putting additional strain on rivers and aquifers, making them critical for sustainable agriculture (Elliott <i>et al.</i>, 2014).
11 Tech for Sustainability	Adopting digital technologies across the agricultural supply chain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farm machinery automation, sensors and remote satellite data, Artificial Intelligence and machine learning have the potential to play a critical role in ensuring the traceability of agricultural food products, which has become an essential requirement for most enterprises (Ben Ayed and Hanana, 2021).
12 Impacts on Food and Health	Sub-field of food safety: foodborne diseases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The interaction of climate change and food production, distribution and consumption methods can impact the occurrence of foodborne diseases (Hall <i>et al.</i>, 2002). • There are still gaps in understanding how ecosystem disease regulation works and how human activities can influence disease dynamics in an indirect and long-term manner (Lindahl and Grace, 2015).
13 Climate and Global Food	Changes in production and consumption to meet future food and ecosystem service needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptation of the global agriculture and food system can help reduce the negative effects of climate change while capitalising on positive outcomes (Alexander <i>et al.</i>, 2018). • Tinkering with existing systems is insufficient; significant transformations are required to achieve long-term results (Smith and Gregory, 2013).
14 Emissions and Agriculture	Ozone's impact on the climate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elevated ozone levels usually result in reduced photosynthesis, accelerated senescence, decreased growth and lower yields (Booker <i>et al.</i>, 2009) • While previous adaptation strategies have assisted farmers in dealing with changing environments, the limited benefits of adaptation highlight the importance of mitigating ozone precursors to secure regional and global food production (Teixeira <i>et al.</i>, 2011).
15 Sustainable Food Research	Solutions to reduce soil salinity and increase plant resilience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crop research should prioritise the development of crop varieties that can maintain or improve yields with less water input (Bertolino <i>et al.</i>, 2019). • Studying stomatal development is critical to understanding crop plant productivity and water-use efficiency, which benefits natural ecosystems and agricultural systems.
16 Agri-Sustainability Future	Outlook to the future	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forests and trees, as renewable resources, are of fundamental importance to humanity (Blaser and Gregersen, 2013). • It will be possible to resist the rise of emerging epidemics and health problems by implementing the potential of microbial strains for producing food and chemical goods (Hakalehto, 2020).

Supplementary Table S4.

Cross-classification of documents according to Clusters and ASJC categories (in %)

Cluster	Health Science	Life Science	Multi-disciplinary	Physical Sciences	Social Sciences & Humanities	Total
Food Choices	14.79	32.33	1.10	26.58	25.21	100
Water Management	4.01	18.34	2.01	57.59	18.05	100
Climate Adaptation	1.78	28.19	2.67	38.28	29.08	100
Sustainable Crop Tech	5.94	51.16	2.64	26.07	14.19	100
Food Systems and Urban Farming	4.67	25.68	1.95	33.07	34.63	100
Sustainable Soil Management	5.24	36.29	4.03	41.94	12.50	100
Sustainable Agriculture and Aquaculture	2.58	25.75	6.44	50.21	15.02	100
Climate-Agro Impacts	3.43	25.32	2.15	44.64	24.46	100
Sustainable Bioenergy	4.91	29.91	3.13	46.88	15.18	100
Impacts on Water and Crops	5.62	29.21	7.87	41.57	15.73	100
Tech for Sustainability	2.19	25.55	2.19	43.80	26.28	100
Impacts on Food and Health	20.93	34.88	0.00	33.72	10.47	100
Climate and Global Food	10.00	41.25	7.50	28.75	12.50	100
Emissions and Agriculture	5.00	10.00	0.00	70.00	15.00	100
Sustainable Food Research	9.09	72.73	0.00	9.09	9.09	100
Agri-Sustainability Future	0.00	66.67	0.00	33.33	0.00	100
Total	5.97	30.55	3.03	39.92	20.53	100

Supplementary Table S5.

Top five Scopus subject areas for each cluster according to the ASJC codes

Cluster	1st Scopus Subject Area	2nd Scopus Subject Area	3rd Scopus Subject Area	4th Scopus Subject Area	5th Scopus Subject Area
1 Food Choices	Food Science: 8.5%	Strategy and Management: 8.2%	Environmental Science (all): 7.4%	Environmental Engineering: 5.6%	Horticulture: 5.2%
2 Water Management	Water Science and Technology 17%	Geography, Planning and Development: 10%	Environmental Engineering: 6.3%	Management, Monitoring, Policy and Law: 6.3%	Agronomy and Crop Science: 5.2%
3 Climate Adaptation	Geography, Planning and Development: 10.4%	Agronomy and Crop Science: 8%	Development: 6%	Environmental Science (all): 6%	Renewable Energy, Sustainability and the Environment: 5%
4 Sustainable Crop Tech	Plant Science: 17.2%	Agronomy and Crop Science: 9.2%	Agricultural and Biological Sciences (all): 7.6%	Environmental Science (all): 5.6%	Food Science: 4.3%
5 Food Systems and Urban Farming	Geography, Planning and Development: 10.5%	Food Science: 7.4%	Renewable Energy, Sustainability and the Environment: 6.6%	Environmental Science (all): 6.2%	Agricultural and Biological Sciences (all): 5.1%
6 Sustainable Soil Management	Agronomy and Crop Science: 8.5%	Agricultural and Biological Sciences (all): 7.3%	Ecology: 7.3%	Environmental Science (all): 7.3%	Management, Monitoring, Policy and Law: 5.6%
7 Sustainable Agriculture and Aquaculture	Environmental Engineering: 11.2%	Geography, Planning and Development: 10.3%	Ecology: 8.2%	Multidisciplinary: 6.4%	Ecology, Evolution, Behavior and Systematics: 5.2%
8 Climate-Agro Impacts	Environmental Engineering: 11.6%	Geography, Planning and Development: 10.3%	Agricultural and Biological Sciences (all): 6.4%	Atmospheric Science: 6.4%	Food Science: 6%
9 Sustainable Bioenergy	Agronomy and Crop Science 8%	Environmental Science (all) 6.3%	Geography, Planning and Development 6.3%	Ecology 6%	Renewable Energy, Sustainability and the Environment 5%
10 Impacts on Water and Crops	Agronomy and Crop Science 8%	Multidisciplinary 8%	Environmental Science (all) 5.6%	Geography, Planning and Development 5.1%	Public Health, Environmental and Occupational Health 5.1%
11 Tech for Sustainability	Geography, Planning and Development 8.8%	Renewable Energy, Sustainability and the Environment 6.6%	Food Science 5.8%	Engineering (all) 5.1%	Horticulture 5.1%
12 Impacts on Food and Health	Food Science 15.1%	Public Health, Environmental and Occupational Health 5.8%	Animal Science and Zoology 4.6%	Environmental Science (all) 4.6%	Geography, Planning and Development 4.6%

Supplementary Table S5.

Top five Scopus subject areas for each cluster according to the ASJC codes - Continued

Cluster	1st Scopus Subject Area	2nd Scopus Subject Area	3rd Scopus Subject Area	4th Scopus Subject Area	5th Scopus Subject Area
13 Climate and Global Food	Agricultural and Biological Sciences (all) 10%	Agronomy and Crop Science 7.5%	Environmental Science (all) 7.5%	Multidisciplinary 7.5%	Plant Science 6.3%
14 Emissions and Agriculture	Environmental Science (all) 25%	Management, Monitoring, Policy and Law 20%	Renewable Energy, Sustainability and the Environment 10%	Water Science and Technology 10%	Agricultural and Biological Sciences (all) 5%
15 Sustainable Food Research	Agronomy and Crop Science 18.2%	Agricultural and Biological Sciences (all) 9.1%	Biochemistry, Genetics and Molecular Biology (all) 9.1%	Drug Discovery 9.1%	Food Science 9.1%
16 Agri-Sustainability Future	Agricultural and Biological Sciences (all) 33.3%	Media Technology 33.3%	Food Science 33.3%	-	-

Note: The percentages indicate the share of papers classified in an ASJC in each cluster.

Supplementary Table S6.
Actionable directions for future research

What to study?	How to study?
<p align="center">Topic 1: Agro-ecosystems</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which new farming systems and simulation models could advance sustainability of agro-ecosystems? • How can incorporating a network perspective or circular bioeconomy transform current agro-ecosystems? • What new strategies could improve climate change adaptation at farm level? 	<p align="center">Systems approach lens</p> <p>Applying a systems approach lens can advance our understanding of how different parts of the food system interact and assist in providing more efficient solutions to complex problems</p>
<p align="center">Topic 2: Technology</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How can digital technologies, machine learning and gene editing assist in building more sustainable food systems? • What are the strengths and weaknesses of adopting bio-, nano- and green-technologies? • What is the role of AI in mitigating climate change and how can we best leverage it? 	<p align="center">Innovative and diverse simulation-based research</p> <p>Simulation methodology is not yet well-developed in the mainstream food sector research but by learning from the neighbouring health field, such methodology could be effectively applied</p>
<p align="center">Topic 3: Bioenergy & Emissions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What new solutions for using bioenergy and ozone would benefit the food sector? • What are the key motivations and benefits of voluntary carbon offsetting schemes for different food supply chain actors? • How can we optimise the use of 4th generation of biofuels from social, environmental and economic perspectives? 	<p align="center">Criteria for research funding</p> <p>The funding bodies should reconsider their criteria for awarding funding (especially prestigious funding) to create more equal playing ground for researchers and institutions from low-income and lower-middle-income countries</p>
<p align="center">Topic 4: Food Consumption</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How can consumers' choices be modified so they choose more sustainable diets? • What types of diets have the best and the worst environmental, economic and social impact? • What is the role of food supply chain actors in enabling sustainable food consumption? 	<p align="center">Interdisciplinary teams</p> <p>Future research teams should be assembled taking into account a systems approach lens in terms of the breadth of expertise needed to contribute to solving complex problems, as well as team composition in terms of ethnicity, gender, career stage and country of origin</p>
<p align="center">Research at the intersection of the two fields</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the composition of research teams studying the intersection of the two fields in terms of ethnicity, gender, career stage and country of origin? • Which mechanisms could contribute to a more even allocation of research funding globally and what are the key opportunities and barriers to achieve this? 	

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